

Working title: Behavioural and lifestyle components used alongside GLP-1RAs in interventions for adults with obesity: a systematic scoping review of randomised controlled trials.

Anastasia Searle, Mark Tarrant, Laura Hollands, Jonathan Pinkney, Rebecca Abbott, Michael Nunns, Jill Buckland, Mia Alexander, Sarah Worsley

Background

Affecting over 16% of the world's population, obesity is a disease characterised by the build-up of excess body fat that can impair health (Bowman-Busato et al., 2025; World Health Organisation [WHO], 2025). Although often criticised for its inability to inform on body composition, Body Mass Index (BMI) is still widely used to measure obesity. A person is considered to have obesity if their BMI is 30 or above (this number varies based on race) and to have severe obesity if they have a BMI of 35 or above with comorbidities (40 or above without comorbidities). While the causes of obesity are multi-faceted and are influenced by factors such as psychological trauma, genetic predisposition, hormonal imbalance, comorbidities, environment, social identity, culture, and socioeconomic status (Adams, 2020; Omer, 2020), to date, all major guidelines for weight management advocate the importance of lifestyle (dietary, behaviour) change as part of treatment.

In the past decade, there have been promising advancements in the treatment of obesity utilising glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor agonists (GLP-1 RAs). GLP-1 RAs are glucoregulatory hormones that work to reduce weight by delaying gastric emptying, leading patients to feel satiated for longer, thus decreasing food rumination, and reducing desire to consume excess calories. In 2021, GLP-1 RAs were approved for weight loss in the UK and in 2023, NHS England declared that there would be coverage of semaglutide for some patients for up to two years (NHS, 2023). Major RCTs such as the STEP (Wadden et al., 2021) and SURPASS trials (Rosenstock et al., 2021) testing GLP-1 RAs including semaglutide and tirzepatide, have shown the medications to produce upwards of 15% reduction in body weight. While some trials explicitly utilised behavioural components such

as education on healthy eating and direct contact with dietary specialists to support weight management, the robustness of these interventions is unclear. Furthermore, little information on the protocols for the behavioural supports is available. For example, Wadden et al. (2021) trialled “intensive behavioural therapy” in tandem with semaglutide. However, the content of the therapy is not clearly described, as reference to both “behavioural strategies” in the published article and an “intensive behavioural therapy guide” in the supplementary material are not accompanied by further information. It is unclear how other trials report the behavioural components of their studies, and this requires further investigation through a systematic scoping review.

Research Question

1. What behavioural and/ or lifestyle interventions are utilised alongside treatment with GLP-1RAs in RCTs?

Methods

The protocol for this study was originally published on Prospero, however, after initial searching, it became clear this review was more suitable as a scoping review and was withdrawn from Prospero. Therefore, this working document outlines the protocol and methodology that took place. The data extraction is completed and the review is in the write up stage.

A search for randomised control trials of GLP-1 RAs for weight loss took place. Trials were included that incorporated a behavioural component (e.g., education about diet, counselling, etc.) and or/ lifestyle change intervention. The search incorporated both free-text keywords and controlled vocabulary (e.g., MeSH) where applicable and relevant. The Cochrane RCT filter/hedge (Lefebvre et al., 2024) with modifications was applied. Search terms were agreed upon by the project team. No date limit was set. References were downloaded into Rayyan and de-duplicated.

Information Sources

The following databases and trial registers were searched: Medline (Ovid), APA PsycINFO (Ovid), Embase (Ovid), CINAHL (Ebsco), Web of Science (Clarivate), CENTRAL (Cochrane), ClinicalTrials.gov (www.clinicaltrials.gov/), and the World Health Organization International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (apps.who.int/trialsearch/).

Search Strategy

Databases were searched for titles and abstracts that included terms related to randomised controlled trials (e.g., randomized.ab.), GLP-1 RAs (e.g., glp-1*.tw.), and obesity (e.g., obes*.tw.). Inclusion criteria were RCTs of adults aged 18 or over, treated with GLP-1 RAs with a BMI of 30 or above. Exclusion criteria were RCTs that measured the efficacy of GLP-1RAs in diseases other than obesity (i.e., diabetes, alcoholism, etc.). An example of the search strategy for Ovid MEDLINE(R) is provided below:

Ovid MEDLINE(R) and In-Process, In-Data-Review & Other Non-Indexed Citations <1946 to March 12, 2025>

- 1 randomized controlled trial.pt.
- 2 controlled clinical trial.pt.
- 3 randomized.ab.
- 4 placebo.ab.
- 5 drug therapy.fs.
- 6 randomly.ab.
- 7 trial.ab.
- 8 groups.ab.
- 9 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8
- 10 exp animals/ not humans.sh.
- 11 9 not 10
- 12 glp-1*.tw.
- 13 glucagon like peptid* 1.tw.
- 14 *Glucagon-Like Peptide 1/

- 15 *Glucagon-Like Peptide-1 Receptor Agonists/
 16 semaglutide.tw.
 17 liraglutide.tw.
 18 tirzepatide.tw.
 19 dulaglutide.tw.
 20 retatrutide.tw.
 21 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20
 22 (Weight adj2 (over or loss* or gain* or increas* or decreas* or management or
 control* or reduc* or change*)).tw.
 23 ((body mass index or bmi) adj2 (loss* or gain* or increas* or decreas* or control* or
 reduc* or change*)).tw.
 24 overweight.tw.
 25 obes*.tw.
 26 exp Obesity/
 27 body weight.tw.
 28 *Body Weight/
 29 *Overweight/
 30 exp Body Weight/
 31 exp Overweight/
 32 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31
 33 9 and 21 and 32

Supplementary methods

Additional relevant studies were identified by carrying out citation searching (forward and backwards) of the included papers using Web of Science, Scopus, and Primo.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The PICOT framework (see below) was applied during the search strategy to identify relevant studies.

Participants/population:

Participants must be adults (18 or above), and considered to have obesity according to cultural specifications (BMI of 30 and above or 27 and above with comorbidities for Western populations, 23 and above for Asian populations).

Intervention:

Trials measuring the efficacy of pharmacological treatment of obesity with GLP-1RAs including (but not limited to) semaglutide, dulaglutide, tirzepatide, liraglutide, exenatide, and retatrutide. The trials must include behavioural support components and occur for 24 or more weeks.

Comparator(s)/control:

GLP-1RA versus placebo.

Outcomes

Total weight lost from trial commencement.

Study design

Randomised controlled trials

Date Limit

No date limit

Geographical Context

No restrictions

Language

Where available, studies that can be translated to English will be considered for inclusion.

Data Selection

Each record identified through the search underwent an initial screening of its title and abstract by two independent reviewers (AS screened all articles, MA and SW split screening) to exclude irrelevant studies. Any disagreements were resolved through discussion. Following this, the full text of the remaining records was assessed by two independent reviewers to determine eligibility. When disagreements arose, these were resolved by discussion. Records excluded at the full-text stage were coded based on the primary reason for exclusion.

Data Extraction

Relevant information from the included trials was extracted by the first author.

Data was extracted in relation to the following:

- Author details (author names, title, date of publication, doi, etc.)

- Funding and conflict of interest information
- Sample characteristics (sample size, age, gender, BMI, ethnicity, relevant comorbidities, socioeconomic status, etc.)
- Methods of behavioural support participants receive:
 - For example: counselling (face to face or online, one on one or in groups), education about diet and fitness, self-monitoring, goal setting, feedback and evaluation, social support, etc.)
- Mention of theory in the behavioural support provided (i.e., behaviour change techniques, cognitive-behavioural therapy)
- Behavioural support service provider (e.g., dietician, psychologist, etc.)
- Medication type, dosage, intervals of dosage increase, titration strategy
- Comparator details (intervention versus placebo)
- Outcomes (total weight lost since trial commencement)
- Length of intervention (how long drug administered, how long lifestyle intervention administered)
- Psychosocial outcomes (QoL (WHOQoL/ IWQoL Lite, SF 36 scores)
- Findings relating to weight loss (e.g., percentage change in body weight, Kg lost, change in BMI)
- Inclusion and exclusion criteria of the RCTs

Analysis and Synthesis

Descriptions of each study were tabulated for the items listed under Data Extraction with lifestyle interventions categorised using a bespoke framework. The bespoke framework took guidance from the Behaviour Change Technique Taxonomy (Michie et al., 2013), where trials were categorised, where applicable, into the 16 groups of behaviour change techniques (BCTs). Any categories outside of the BCT groups were added, when necessary. The

following behavioural technique groups were noted to be present across trials: Counselling (addressing mental health or behaviour change), education about diet and fitness, self-monitoring, goal setting, feedback (encouragement and evaluation), social support, and meal replacement (this is not a BCT group but is related to the group “Repetition and substitution”).

Data were synthesised narratively. Available data on lifestyle interventions were recorded to highlight depth of detail provided, frequency of intervention, location of information (e.g., primary published article, protocol, appendix), type, quantity and length of sessions, and whether the support was based on psychological theory or therapeutic modalities. Pooled means of weight lost and QoL scores will be reported.

These results could potentially indicate important criteria for lifestyle interventions to be included alongside GLP-1 RA treatment, along with criteria for reporting interventions in published articles and/ or protocols.

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